

Performance of Grade 9 Students in Technology and Livelihood Education

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Abstract:- This study dealt on the performance Grade 9 students in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) in the public high schools of Urdaneta City, Pangasinan. The study adopted the descriptive method using a content-validated survey questionnaire determining the profile of the respondents, the level of written and hands-on performance in the given field of specialization, the problems that encountered by Teachers in teaching Home-Economics Cookery and Information and Communication and significant relationship between the profile variables, written and hands-on performance of the students. Data were analyzed using frequency count, percentage distribution, weighted mean, Chi-square and Pearson's. Majority of the respondents are female. Most of them are taking up Cookery as field of specialization. Concerning the employment profile of their parents as respondents' parents, most of them are blue collar job. As to their educational attainment, majority of the students' parents finished high school and college. On the income profile of the respondents' parents, most of the respondents belong to families with relatively low income.

The data gathered through the questionnaire-checklist indicates that the written exam of Cookery and Information Communication Technology of Grade 9 Technology and Livelihood students is approximately normal. The Hands-on performance of Cookery and ICT Grade 9 students is with descriptive equivalent of satisfactory.

Moreover, findings show that there is no significant relationship between the Specialization, Highest Educational Attainment of Father and Mother and Monthly Family Income and Written Exam of the students must be rejected. While the profile of the students as to Highest Educational Attainment of Father and Mother and Monthly Family Income are directly correlated with the Hands-on Performance of the respondents.

On the basis of the findings, this study makes recommendations such as the school may request a Free TESDA Training to the parents and have the opportunities to be employed in a certain area where they are capable of, the school may allocate enough fund for the teaching aids utilized in TLE subjects, particularly in cookery and ICT and the Education Sector should grant more scholarship to the students and proposed a list of training / seminars to enhance the performance of Grade TLE Teachers.

Keywords:- Performance, Technology and Livelihood Education.

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology and Livelihood Education in the global community plays an important role because it allows students to enrich their knowledge and develop technical skills that will transform their lives. Education plays an important role as it shapes the minds of young learners in enclosing all bodies of knowledge that are related to livelihood education, home economics, and even the world we live in. Teaching and learning the subject let the student get out of their comfort zones and eventually venture into the realm of "knowing the world" and even let those strands of learning change their lives ultimately and enable them to meet global demands.

Learners are to be equipped with critical thinking skills, developed through proper exercise of the mind and fed with accurate information. In learning TLE, proper knowledge and skills in agriculture, home economics, entrepreneurship, and Information and Communications Technology (ICT) are required to understand it. This can be better attained by thoroughly understanding the very reason why there is indeed a need to learn these things, and that is for their own survival.

Academic Performance is a result of interplay of different factors in the school. Different studies point out varying forces that may affect how well or how low students could get while in school. As revealed by Chetty, Friedman, & Rockoff (2014), it was shown in the study conducted that teachers have substantial impacts on their students' academic and life-long success including some characteristics of effective classroom environments, including teachers' organizational skills and interactions with students.

In educational institutions, success is measured by academic performance, or how well a student meets standards set out by local government and the institution itself. As career competition grows ever fiercer in the working world, the importance of students doing well in school has caught the attention of parents, legislators and government education departments. Although education is not the only road to success in the working world, much effort is made to identify, evaluate, track and encourage the progress of students in schools. Parents care about the academic performance of their children because they believe that good academic results will provide more career choices and job security. Schools, though invested in fostering good academic habits for the same reason, are also often influenced by concerns about the school's reputation and the possibility of monetary aid from government institutions, which can be a turning point on the overall academic performance of the school (Bell, M. updated 2016).

Academic achievement of pupils refers to the knowledge attained and skills developed in school subjects. So, academic achievement means the achievement of students in the academic subjects in relation to their knowledge attaining ability or degree of competence in school tasks usually measured by standardized tests and expressed in grades or units based on pupil's performance (Parveen et.al, 2013).

Performance-based assessment is the real assessment that determines tasks which require detailed performance, providing the learner a chance to observe and apply acquired knowledge, learned either directly or through constructive learning, as soon as s/he starts to build new perceptions and relationships that connect learned facts and concepts which enable him/her to make correct decisions in order to overcome task-related problems (Bloxham & Carver, 2014). Studies on performance-based assessment have been widely conducted. It is believed that performance-based assessment is the potential to know to what extent the students have authentically mastered the materials and bring good effects.

In the Philippines, the K to 12 Program has started its roots in the early parts of the 21st Century through Republic Act 9155 otherwise known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001. This law defined the roles of every personnel of the Department of Education for delivery of quality educational programs, projects and services (DepEd Order No. 1, s. 2003).

In the year 2013, Republic Act 9155 was supplemented by Republic Act 10533 otherwise known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2013, more popularly known as the K to 12 Program which came into the Philippine Educational System through President Benigno "Noy" Aquino. This law has caused a major change not only in the curriculum of the Filipino Educational System, but also, an impact on the lives of the learners as well as their parents and other stakeholders of the school.

In terms of academics these changes created equivalent revolution in the training of teachers, thus, some seasoned teachers are even taught to "unlearn" and learn new other things as strategies and techniques in teaching the subjects, and among these subjects.

Usual classroom situations in TLE, entail chalkboard activities, or, for some situations, students are required to clean, construct wooden projects or repair classroom furniture, cook, or bake without proper consideration of what knowledge, skills or even attitudes are to be developed or the manner how all these are to be learned with accuracy. As a result, some learners complete the subject and move to the next learning area without the actual measurement of whatever new things have to be learned.

Despite mentioned significance of the subject, to an extent, this subject has not been receiving attention as much as the others. With the scenario herein presented, it is of the issue that the teaching of TLE should give emphasis on making each learner have concrete experiences on the concepts they have to learn. Thus, it boils down to the classic view on "learning by

doing" and can only be attained when proper materials, facilities and equipment are actually used by students, correlating these to their actual performance of the tasks expected of them. The performances of the students are at issue because the specialized field in TLE is not taken seriously.

Several problems were identified further that affect the learners' performance among Public High Schools in Urdaneta City, Pangasinan. First is the financial capability of the students' which based on teaching experiences and shared views from the TLE teachers and other subject teacher in different learning areas, majority of the students belong to the poor family. During the practicum, some of the students cannot afford the cost of ingredients to be used. The second problem becomes worse school facilities, materials, tools and equipment is lacking which students often bring their own materials. Laboratory Room is not also available in the school so the students will use the study shed. Desired outputs of the students will never guarantee to the prescribed outcome of their performance. Some schools do have facilities and equipment but are limited to the number of enrollee specialized in cookery and ICT. Lastly, some teachers do not have qualifications and expertise in teaching TLE. Teachers are jack of all traits particularly in their various assigned teaching loads. Human resource should have employed teachers and assigned them in their field of expertise. This results to failure in the learning process. It is within these perspectives that this study shall be working with.

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

This study aimed to determine the performance of Grade 9 students in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE), Home Economics- Cookery and Information and Communication Technology in the public high schools of Urdaneta City, Pangasinan and it also looked into the problems met by the Teachers.

Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the student respondents in terms of:
 - a. sex;
 - b. parent's highest educational attainment;
 - c. occupation of father;
 - d. occupation of mother;
 - e. monthly family income?
2. What is the academic performance of the students in the Home Economics - Cookery and Information and Communication Technology?
3. What are the problems encountered by the teachers in the conduct of laboratory performance of the students in Home Economics-Cookery and Information and Communication Technology?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile variables and written and hands on performance of the students?
5. Based on findings, what are the training's and seminars can be proposed to enhance the teaching of TLE teachers specialized in Home Economics-Cookery and Information and Communication Technology?

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study employed the descriptive design in determining the performance of Grade 9 students in Technology and Livelihood Education. Descriptive research design is a type of research method that is used to get information on the current status of a person or an object. It is used to describe what is in existence with respect to conditions or variables that are found in a given situation. On the other hand, the correlation was adopted to secure the presence or absence of a significant relationship between the independent data and dependent measurements.

B. Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study are the 203 students enrolled in TLE and 6 subject teachers specialized in: Information and Communication Technology and Home-Economics Cookery. The participating schools are Cabuloan National High School, Camantiles National High School, and Lananpin National High School.

C. Statistical Treatment

Based on the study's research problems, the gathered data were analyzed, tabulated, organized, and computed. Frequency counts, percentage distributions, and weighted averages were used to process the raw data using descriptive statistics.

For the question on the profile of the participants on sex, educational attainment of parents, monthly family income, frequency counts, percentages, and mean were used;

For the written and hands on performance in TLE specialized in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Home Economics – Cookery, descriptive measures of statistics (frequency counts, mean, standard deviation, CU, kurtosis, and skewness) were employed.

For the problems met encountered by the teachers in the conduct of laboratory performance of the students in Home Economics-Cookery and Information and Communication Technology, frequency counts and rank were employed.

For the relationship between the profile variables mentioned, the written and hand on performance in TLE's Spearman rank coefficient of correlation chi-square and ETA square was used.

Specific problem number 5 is the proposed intervention to enhance the teaching of TLE students in Home Economics—Cookery and Information Communication Technology that will improve students' performance.

The aid of a statistics expert was employed to establish the credibility of statistical findings and interpretations.

III. RESULTS

This study focused on determining the performance of Grade 9 students in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) in the public high schools of Urdaneta City, Pangasinan. Specifically, the study sought to look for answers on the: 1) personal profile of the respondents; 2) level of written and hands on performance of the Grade 9 in students in TLE:: Home Economics – cookery and Information and Communication Technology; 3) problems encountered by the teachers in the conduct of laboratory performance of the students in Home Economics-Cookery and Information and Communication Technology; 4) significant relationship between the profile variables and written and hands on performance of the students; and 5) what proposed intervention can be suggested or recommended to enhance the teaching of TLE that will improve students' performance.

The descriptive method of research was utilized in this study, since it involved the assessment of the performance and acquired skills by the respondents particularly in cookery, Information and Computer Technology. There was a total of 203 students and 6 teachers' respondents who participated in the study and responded to the questionnaire. The data gathering instrument used was the questionnaire, and later supplemented with instructed or casual conversation.

Analyses of the gathered data were done with the use of proper statistical tools such as descriptive measure of statistics like frequency counts, mean, standard deviation, CU, kurtosis and skewness. Finally, for the relationship between the profile variables mentioned, the written and hand on performance in TLE, Spearman rank coefficient of correlation chi-square and ETA were used.

Given the problems identified in this study the following are the salient findings:

Majority of the respondents are female students whose specialization in TLE is cookery. Also, majority of the respondents' parents finished high school who are employed in blue-collar jobs, and the majority of them have a monthly family income of below the poverty threshold, which is PHP 7890.

The level of written and hands on performance of the students in TLE using laboratory materials and equipment in Information and Communication Technology and Cookery both somewhat fall below normal yet normally distributed. Both of them obtained a descriptive equivalent of "approximately normal".

Students were highly motivated to learn in classroom engagements, specifically when lessons were integrated with performance-based tasks. It could be gleaned visibly that the level of written and hands on performance of the students in TLE using laboratory materials and equipment in Home Economics-Cookery is highly accepted.

IV. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study the recommendations below are hereby offered:

1. The school may request a Free TESDA Training to the parents and opportunities to employed in a certain area where they are capable of.
2. The school may allocate enough fund for the teaching aids utilized in TLE subjects, particularly in cookery and ICT.
3. For the total number of enrolled students, the library may offer an adequate number of books or printed educational resources.
4. The procurement of tools and equipment for student and faculty members' educational purposes maybe given priority by administrators.
5. The Education Sector should grant more scholarship to the students.
6. One's gained information, abilities, and attitudes have a significant impact on one's ability to perform exceptionally well, for both teachers and students. To update teachers on new technology, trends, and challenges relevant to their area of competence, administrators may consider sending teachers teaching in cookery may be send to training, seminars related to their specialization or even conduct the same as in service training.
7. The Grade 9 TLE teachers handling Cookery and ICT shall be advised to utilize the propose training and seminar to enhance their teaching.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Bell, M. (2011). Define Academic Performance http://www.ehow.com/about_5082305_definitionacademic-research-writing.html
- [2]. Bloxham, S. & Carver, M. (2014). Assessment for learning in higher education. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*,39(1),123–126. doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2013.797652
- [3]. Chetty, R., Friedman, J. N., & Rockoff, J. E. (2014). Measuring the impacts of teachers I:Evaluating Bias in Teacher Value-Added Estimates. *American Economic Review*, 104(9), 2593-2632.
- [4]. Parveen. A, Noor-Ul-Amin. S, Nazir. S. K. 2013. Comparative study of the academic achievement of 10th class boys and girls studying in different high schools of District Pulwama of (J&K). *Journal of Education Research and Behavioral Sciences*, 2, pp 20-27.